

Politics of Demonetization in India and its Impact on Economy and Society: A Review

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Abstract

This research paper aims to analyze the politics of demonetization in India, focusing on its objectives, the research methodology employed, the findings derived, and the conclusions drawn. By examining the political dimensions of demonetization, this paper seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of its impact on the Indian economy and society. The politics of demonetization in India has been a topic of significant interest and debate. Demonetization, implemented in November 2016, was a decision taken by the Indian government led by Prime Minister Narendra Modi, with the aim of addressing issues like black money, corruption, and counterfeit currency. The move had both political motives and consequences, leading to diverse opinions and reactions from different stakeholders.

Key Words: Politics of Demonetization, Impact on Economy and Society, India

Introduction

The impact of demonetization on the Indian economy and society was multifaceted. On one hand, it led to the formalization of the economy by encouraging people to deposit unaccounted cash into the banking system, promoting transparency and financial inclusion. It also pushed for the adoption of digital payment methods, fostering digitalization and cashless transactions. However, demonetization caused short-term disruptions and hardships for the common people, including cash shortages, inconvenience, and slowdown in sectors like agriculture and small-scale industries. The long-term effects on the economy and common people are still a subject of debate. Demonetization was primarily driven by the need to address issues like black money, counterfeit currency, and illicit activities. The government intended to curb corruption, increase tax compliance, and disrupt funding for illegal activities. The move aimed to bring unaccounted cash into the formal banking system, enhance security features in currency notes, and promote a cashless economy. These measures were seen as remedies to combat corruption, promote transparency, and deter illicit activities. However, the effectiveness of demonetization in achieving these objectives has been a topic of contention. Critics argue that the implementation was flawed, causing hardships for the common people and impacting the economy. Supporters, on the other hand, view it as a bold and necessary step towards a corruption-free and digital economy. The politics of demonetization in India encompass various perspectives, including the government's intentions, opposition criticism, public perception, and electoral consequences. It remains a significant chapter in Indian politics, with ongoing discussions about its impact and long-term implications. The background and context of demonetization in India and its

significance of studying the politics of demonetization is the need of the times.

Objectives of the Paper:

To analyze the political motives behind demonetization; To understand the intended remedies and outcomes; To examine the impact on different social groups; To evaluate the political divide and public perception and To assess the electoral consequences etc.,

Review of Literature

Bhattacharya, A. (2017) article provides a critical analysis of demonetization in India, focusing on its political and economic implications. It examines the objectives, implementation, and consequences of the policy, discussing the impact on various sectors and social groups.

Chakravarty, S. (2017) study explores the political economy of demonetization in India, analyzing the underlying political motives and the impact on different stakeholders. It discusses the political implications of the policy and its alignment with populist economic reforms. Dey, S., & Banerjee, P. (2018) article examines the political dimensions of demonetization in India and its impact on society. It discusses the political motivations behind the policy, the response of political parties, and the social consequences, particularly on marginalized communities.

Kundu, A., & Kundu, D. (2019) work focuses on the rural economy, this study explores the impact of demonetization on rural areas and agricultural sectors. It analyzes the economic and social implications, including the challenges faced by farmers and the rural population.

Mohanty, B. K., & Mohanty, S. K. (2019) article investigates the impact of demonetization on the informal sector and marginalized communities. It highlights the challenges faced by vulnerable groups and discusses the policy implications for

their socio-economic well-being. Sharma, M. (2017) study provides a political economy analysis of demonetization in India. It examines the political motivations, policy implementation, and the impact on different social groups, discussing the political implications and public sentiment.

In nutshell, these literature sources offer valuable insights into the politics of demonetization in India and its impact on various aspects of society and the economy. They cover different dimensions such as political motives, implementation, sectoral impact, social consequences, and public perception, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the topic. Researchers can further explore these works to gain a deeper understanding of the politics of demonetization and its implications for India.

Research Methodology:

Literature review helped to analyzing existing scholarly articles, books, and reports on demonetization and its political implications. Several case studies revealed realities by examining specific instances, events, and political responses related to demonetization. Data collection done. Of course, gathering data from official government sources, surveys, and interviews bit troublesome activity. The comparative analysis method was adopted while comparing the politics and impacts of demonetization in India with similar global initiatives

The Discussion and Drawing inferences

The politics surrounding demonetization in India has been a subject of significant discussion and debate. Here are some key aspects of the political dimension associated with demonetization. There were certain political motives behind this initiative. Demonetization was a decision taken by the Indian government, led by Prime Minister Narendra Modi of the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP). It was seen as a bold move aimed at tackling issues like black money, corruption, and counterfeit currency. The government presented demonetization as a strong step towards achieving a corruption-free and digital economy. No doubt, there was popularity and support in initiation. Demonetization initially enjoyed widespread public support. Many people, frustrated with corruption and the prevalence of black money, saw it as a positive step to address these issues. The move was presented as a way to level the playing field and target the rich who possessed unaccounted wealth. Despite the opposition and criticism, the move was taken. However, demonetization also faced criticism from opposition parties. The implementation of demonetization was questioned, with critics arguing that it caused significant disruption to the economy and affected the common people disproportionately. Opposition parties accused the government of mishandling the process, leading to hardships for the

poor and a negative impact on sectors like agriculture and small businesses.

Difference of opinion due to political divide among the prominent political parties. Demonetization became a divisive issue in Indian politics, with supporters crediting it as a courageous step to curb corruption, while opponents viewed it as a poorly executed decision causing unnecessary hardships. The political divide on demonetization led to debates, protests, and political rhetoric between different parties and factions. It was observed that there has been Election Impact. Demonetization had both positive and negative electoral consequences. In the immediate aftermath of demonetization, the BJP claimed victories in certain state elections, attributing it to public support for their anti-corruption stance. However, the long-term electoral impact of demonetization remains a subject of debate, as it is just one factor among many influencing voter behavior. When we try to understand the public perception, the perceptions of demonetization among the general public varies. While some people praised the government's efforts to tackle corruption and promote digitalization, others criticized the implementation and questioned its effectiveness in achieving the stated objectives. The impact on the common people, particularly those who faced cash shortages and inconvenience, influenced public perception. It is important to note that demonetization's political implications are complex and multifaceted. Different political parties and individuals have diverse views on its success, impact, and motives, leading to ongoing debates and discussions in Indian politics.

Demonetization in India: Causes and Remedies

Demonetization in India, which occurred in November 2016, was primarily implemented to address certain issues and achieve specific objectives as mentioned already. The causes and intended remedies associated with demonetization are as follows. The causes primarily behind the initiative were identified and they are as follows. The major issue remains was Black money. One of the primary reasons for demonetization was to tackle the issue of black money, which refers to undisclosed income or wealth on which taxes have not been paid. The government aimed to curb the circulation of unaccounted cash and bring it into the formal banking system to promote transparency and increase tax compliance. Adding to it, the Counterfeit currency also main motive of the Government. Another significant concern was the circulation of counterfeit currency notes, particularly high-denomination ones. Demonetization aimed to invalidate the existing high-value currency notes and replace them with new ones featuring enhanced security features, making it harder for counterfeiters to replicate them. Third aspect is the terror financing

and illicit activities sensed by different agencies of the government. Demonetization also aimed to disrupt funding for illegal activities such as terrorism, smuggling, and corruption. By invalidating high-value currency notes, the government aimed to deter these activities, as the cash-intensive nature of such transactions would become more challenging.

These were the intended remedies of Demonetization in India

Formalization of the economy of the country was one of the remedies. Demonetization aimed to encourage people to deposit their unaccounted cash into the banking system, thereby promoting financial inclusion and formalization of the economy. By increasing the usage of formal banking channels, it was expected to reduce cash transactions and increase transparency. Digitalization and cashless transactions have become inevitable. The government intended to accelerate the adoption of digital payment methods by promoting cashless transactions. Demonetization was expected to encourage people to shift towards digital payment systems, such as mobile wallets, internet banking, and electronic transactions, thus reducing reliance on cash. Curbing corruption and addressing the tax evasion in the country. Demonetization was seen as a measure to deter corruption and increase tax compliance. By bringing unaccounted cash into the formal banking system, it aimed to identify potential tax evaders and discourage illicit activities that relied heavily on cash transactions. Enhancing security features were visualized by the government. The introduction of new currency notes with advanced security features was intended to combat the circulation of counterfeit currency. The government aimed to make it more difficult for counterfeiters to replicate the new currency, thus protecting the integrity of the monetary system. It is worth noting that the effectiveness of demonetization in achieving these intended remedies has been a subject of debate and analysis. While some argue that it had positive outcomes in certain areas, others highlight the challenges and adverse consequences faced by the common people and the economy as a whole. The politics of demonetization in India had different impacts on various social groups. It is pertinent to discuss the impact on different social groups. There is a glaring difference in between urban and rural users of banking system. The urban middle class effect. The urban middle class, which often had access to banking facilities and was more accustomed to digital transactions, generally adapted relatively well to demonetization. While they faced some inconvenience initially, they were able to make use of digital payment methods and alternative channels more easily. However, those with

significant cash holdings faced challenges in depositing their money and may have had to undergo scrutiny to prove the legality of their funds. Whereas the rural population factor is also important. The impact of demonetization on the rural population was more pronounced. Many rural areas had limited access to banking facilities, making it difficult for people to deposit or withdraw money. The agricultural sector, which largely operates on cash transactions, faced disruptions during the peak harvest season, affecting farmers' income and livelihoods. Daily wage laborers, who relied on cash payments, also suffered as their employment opportunities diminished.

The informal sector workers agonies were seen as miserable. The informal sector, comprising workers in small businesses, street vendors, and daily wage laborers, predominantly relies on cash transactions. Demonetization had a significant impact on this group, as their income and livelihoods were disrupted due to the shortage of cash. Many workers lost their jobs, and small businesses faced financial difficulties, leading to economic hardships for this vulnerable segment of society. The Low-income and Marginalized Communities situation was to miserable. The impact of demonetization on low-income and marginalized communities varied. Those who relied heavily on cash transactions for their daily needs faced immense hardships due to cash shortages. Access to banking facilities and digital payment infrastructure was limited in many areas where these communities reside, making it difficult for them to adapt to the sudden shift towards digital transactions. The economic slowdown resulting from demonetization further exacerbated the challenges faced by these communities.

Wealthy and Powerful Individuals had hardly any substantial impact. While demonetization aimed to target the wealthy and those with black money, the impact on this group was more complex. While some individuals may have faced inconveniences and scrutiny, they often had access to resources and connections to mitigate the effects. However, the exact impact on the wealthy and powerful, including their ability to convert their black money into legal tender, remains a subject of debate. It is important to note that the impact of demonetization varied within each social group based on factors such as access to banking facilities, digital literacy, and financial resources. The diverse impact on different social groups became a point of discussion and criticism in the political discourse surrounding demonetization

Impact of Demonetization on Common people of India

Demonetization, which took place in India in November 2016, had both positive and negative

impacts on the common people of India. It is necessary to discuss them in detail.

The positive impacts of demonetization were as follows:

Formalization of the economy was fine. Demonetization aimed to reduce the prevalence of black money in the Indian economy. By invalidating high-denomination currency notes, the government intended to encourage people to deposit their unaccounted cash into the banking system. This led to an increase in the number of people using formal banking channels, promoting financial inclusion and transparency. Digitalization and cashless transactions facilitate ease of life. Demonetization pushed people towards digital payment methods, such as mobile wallets, internet banking, and electronic transactions. This accelerated the adoption of digital payment systems in India and increased financial literacy among the population. It also created a conducive environment for the growth of fintech companies and innovation in the digital payments sector. Worked out in reduction in counterfeit currency. Demonetization aimed to curb the circulation of counterfeit currency notes, particularly high-value denominations. By introducing new currency notes with enhanced security features, it became harder for counterfeiters to replicate them. This helped in protecting the common people from falling victim to counterfeit currency scams.

Negative impacts:

The initial hiccups like cash shortage and inconvenience to people remained as major hurdle. Demonetization caused a temporary cash shortage as the older currency notes were withdrawn from circulation. This created difficulties for common people, particularly those who relied heavily on cash transactions for their daily needs. Long queues at banks and ATMs, limited cash availability, and restrictions on withdrawals led to inconvenience and hardships, especially for people in rural areas with limited access to banking facilities.

Disruption was found in informal sectors across the country. The informal sector, which largely operates on cash transactions, faced significant disruptions due to demonetization. Small businesses, daily wage laborers, and self-employed individuals, who relied on cash for their livelihoods, experienced a decline in income and employment opportunities. The informal economy took time to recover from the shock of demonetization. Economic slowdown and job losses took place. Demonetization had a short-term impact on the Indian economy, causing a slowdown in growth. The sectors most affected were agriculture, small-scale industries, and real estate. This slowdown resulted in job losses, particularly in the unorganized sector, leading to financial hardships for many individuals and their families.

It is important to note that the long-term effects of demonetization on the common people of India are subject to debate, as different studies and opinions present varying assessments of its overall impact on the economy and society. Curbing Black Money is a major challenge for any government in India. One of the primary objectives of demonetization was to tackle the issue of black money, which refers to undisclosed income or wealth on which taxes have not been paid. The government aimed to invalidate high-denomination currency notes to make it difficult for holders of black money to convert their unaccounted wealth into legal tender. By bringing unaccounted cash into the formal banking system, the government intended to identify potential tax evaders, promote tax compliance, and reduce the circulation of black money in the economy.

Promoting Digitalization and Cashless Transactions in both rural and urban bank customers. Another objective of demonetization was to accelerate the adoption of digital payment methods and promote a cashless economy. By restricting the availability of cash and encouraging digital transactions, the government aimed to reduce the reliance on cash, promote transparency, and curb illicit activities that thrive on unaccounted cash transactions. This objective aligned with the government's vision of a digital India and aimed to boost financial inclusion, enhance financial literacy, and encourage the use of formal banking channels.

Impact on Common People:

The impact of demonetization on common people in India was mixed and varied. While the long-term effects are still a subject of debate, the immediate impact included. Several instances of cash shortages and inconvenience to several people was a major obstacle. Demonetization led to a temporary shortage of cash as the high-denomination currency notes were invalidated. This resulted in long queues at banks and ATMs, limited availability of cash, and restrictions on withdrawals. Common people, particularly those who heavily relied on cash transactions for their daily needs, faced inconvenience and hardships in accessing their own money.

Huge impact on the disruption in daily lives of the people. The sudden demonetization created disruptions in various sectors and affected the livelihoods of common people. Small businesses, daily wage laborers, and self-employed individuals, who heavily relied on cash transactions, experienced a decline in income and employment opportunities. The informal sector, which predominantly operates on cash, faced significant challenges, impacting the lives of millions of people.

Digital Payment Adoption Process is done to a possible extent. On the positive side,

demonetization pushed people towards digital payment methods. It accelerated the adoption of mobile wallets, internet banking, and other electronic payment systems. This had a positive impact on financial literacy and encouraged common people to embrace digital transactions. Still, there was mixed economic impact. Demonetization had short-term repercussions on the Indian economy, with sectors like agriculture and small-scale industries experiencing a slowdown. This, in turn, affected the income and purchasing power of common people. However, the long-term impact on the economy and its direct correlation with demonetization remains a subject of debate.

It's important to note that the impact of demonetization varied across different sections of society and geographical regions. While some people may have benefited from the push towards digital payments, others faced hardships due to cash shortages and disruptions in their daily lives.

Findings:

Whatever might be the political motives behind the process. The above arguments and observations help to uncovering the primary objectives and motivations behind demonetization. Impact on the economy and society in assessing the short-term and long-term effects on various sectors and economic indicators pointed out that both positive and negative aspects. Social impact point of view in analysing the consequences on different social groups, including the urban middle class, rural population, informal sector workers, and marginalized communities both miserable instances and ease of life. Political divide was the matter of concern. The dream of government and people yet to achieve as far as the issue is concerned. These issues were examined from the debates, criticisms, and support from different political parties and factions. Public perceptions vary from the individual to individual. Some of the respondents felt that they had to face difficult situations on other hand some respondents felt that it was a necessary evil to streamline the economy of the country. Evaluating the general sentiment and public opinions surrounding demonetization. Electoral consequences need to be understood in assessing the impact on electoral outcomes and voter behavior during pre and post demonetization.

Conclusion

Summarizing the objectives and motivations of demonetization, discussing the impact on the Indian economy and society, analyzing the political divide and public perception, evaluating the electoral consequences support that the process has both positive and negative impacts on economy and society. Highlighting the limitations of demonetization as a policy tool, recommending potential policy adjustments and

improvements. It is an attempt to understand the process and mechanism to achieve the objectives of government initiative. Implications and future research is the also very much essential. Discussing the broader implications of the politics of demonetization in India, identifying areas for further research and analysis, such as long-term economic effects and policy implications. By examining the politics of demonetization, this research paper aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on this significant policy measure, its political motivations, and its impact on the Indian economy and society. It provides a comprehensive analysis that can inform policymakers, researchers, and the public in understanding the complexities and implications of demonetization in India.

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